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Land and Groundwater Vulnerability to Leachate and Heavy Metals: HEI-MLGU Environmental Risk Assessment of a Landfill Site

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Abstract

A sanitary landfill must be legally established to manage solid waste safely and environmentally. It is built and operated using engineering principles for efficiency. Mismanagement can lead to significant environmental risks, including groundwater and soil contamination, air pollution, and harmful gas emissions. This study assessed the physico-chemical properties of soil, groundwater, and leachate at the Bayombong Sanitary Landfill in Purok 7, Barangays Magsaysay and Busilac, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, to inform a localized remediation plan. Soil samples from four landfill cells were analyzed for pH, nitrogen, phosphorus, and heavy metal content. Groundwater and leachate samples were examined for ammonia and nitrite concentrations. Results showed slightly acidic soil pH (5.2–6.0), which may limit nutrient availability. Nitrogen levels varied, with Cell 1—closed the longest—showing the highest concentration (106.65 kg/ha), suggesting accumulation through vegetation over time. Phosphorus levels fluctuated, with Cell 3 below optimal range. Cadmium (11.26–15.66 µg/kg) and lead (0.42–0.99 mg/kg) concentrations remained below EPA hazardous thresholds, indicating minimal industrial pollution. Groundwater and leachate samples revealed decreasing ammonia levels (4.2 to 2.0 mg/L) and reduced nitrites, reflecting microbial degradation. However, post-treatment ammonia concentrations still exceeded DENR Water Quality Guidelines. The landfill's clay-loam soil structure likely facilitated heavy metal immobilization, mitigating health risks. The study concludes that while the landfill poses low heavy metal risks, uneven nutrient distribution and residual ammonia require remediation. Recommendations include soil enrichment with compost and green manure, pH correction using lime, establishment of a wastewater treatment facility, enhanced ground, water protection, and ecological rehabilitation using native and nitrogen-fixing plants. Regular monitoring and community awareness programs are also essential. These interventions aim to support sustainable landfill operations in compliance with national environmental standards.

Keywords: ecological Rehabilitation, environmental monitoring, remediation, soil contamination, waste management

INTRODUCTION

Rationale

The increasing generation and accumulation of waste pose serious environmental, economic, and social challenges. Solid waste by-products deposited in landfills negatively impact the surrounding environment and the health of nearby residents.

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Landfilling remains a common waste management method due to its capacity for safe waste disposal across different municipalities. Major landfill types include municipal solid waste, industrial waste, hazardous waste, and the emerging "green waste" landfill (Siddiqua et al., 2022).

In the Philippines, the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 (RA 9003) mandates the construction of sanitary landfills. However, only 245 operational facilities currently serve 478 out of 1,634 local government units (NSWMC & COA, 2021). Weak implementation, limited funding, rapid urbanization, and low public awareness contribute to the country's ongoing solid waste management issues. Inadequate municipal SWM practices can worsen environmental conditions and hinder residents' ability to live healthy, sustainable lives (Ferronato & Torretta, 2019).

Landfills present three major concerns: leachate, greenhouse gases, and toxic emissions. Leachate, rich in harmful physicochemical substances, can contaminate soil and groundwater—threatening a critical resource essential to human health. Additionally, the decomposition of waste generates significant amounts of methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂), which contribute to global anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions (Kumar et al., 2004).

The Bayombong Sanitary Landfill Facility (SLF), established in 2009, plays a crucial role in managing solid waste for the municipality's 25 barangays. In 2023 alone, the facility recorded a total waste generation of 1,421.019 tons, according to the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO) – Environmental Management Division.

This study assessed the impact of leachate percolation from the landfill site on groundwater and soil quality in Barangays Magsaysay and Busilac, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. Groundwater, leachate, and soil samples were collected and analyzed for key physical and chemical properties, including pH, temperature, nitrites, phosphates, and heavy metals (Cd and Hg), using UV-visible spectrophotometry and Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy. The findings aimed to support local officials and urban planners in developing effective waste management and health risk prevention strategies. Aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the study contributes to SDG 6 by promoting clean water and sanitation, SDG 13 by addressing climate-related water quality changes, and SDG 11 by informing sustainable urban development through the proposed Sustainable Remediation Plan. Through this collaborative effort between SMU, MLGU-Bayombong, and the community, the study fosters environmental protection and advances global sustainability.

History of Bayombong Sanitary Landfill

The enactment of RA 9003 was intended to establish a systematic, comprehensive, and ecological approach to solid waste management in line with the country's commitment to sustainable development. Among its key provisions, Section 37 mandated the closure of open and controlled dumpsites, while Section 41 outlined the criteria for the establishment of sanitary landfills. In response to these directives and the increasing volume of solid waste generated by the municipality, a sanitary landfill was established in Purok 7 of Barangays Busilac and Magsaysay, under the leadership of then Municipal Mayor Hon. John Severino G.

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Bagasao. Prior to its establishment, the site underwent a thorough Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), which included an environmental risk assessment, the formulation of an environmental monitoring and management plan, and the conduct of a public hearing to ensure community involvement and transparency. Upon securing all necessary regulatory approvals, the project was issued an Environmental Compliance Certificate (ECC) by the Environmental Management Bureau (EMB) Region II in 2008. Following this, construction of the 8.0296-hectare sanitary landfill commenced, and the facility officially began operations in 2009—marking significant milestone in the municipality's efforts to address the growing challenges of solid waste management.

Environmental Contamination and Pollution

Municipal solid waste includes materials such as plastic, glass, food scraps, metals, and paper from households, offices, commercial, and industrial sources (Umutesi et al., 2018). As defined in RA 9003, it comprises non-hazardous household, commercial, institutional, and industrial waste, as well as street sweepings, construction debris, and agricultural residues—excluding hazardous and infectious waste.

Despite efforts in scientific understanding and rational planning, solid waste management remains a critical challenge for administrations, unable to mitigate its environmental impact fully. Landfill operations are associated with issues like volatile organic compounds, odors, and surface and groundwater contamination, despite meticulous planning and management to prevent environmental and public health risks (Environment Victoria, 2017). Leachate from landfills, containing toxic elements like heavy metals and persistent organic pollutants, poses a significant risk of soil and water contamination. Moreover, hazardous substances such as dioxins and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons are produced by landfills, exacerbating environmental pollution (Njoku et al., 2019).

Water and soil pollution are major threats to the planet, often interconnected as disruption in one sphere affects the other. While sanitary landfilling is a widely used waste disposal method designed to minimize environmental and health risks, leachate contamination remains a concern due to construction and operational flaws. Additionally, landfills produce hazardous substances like dioxins and PAHs, contributing to pollution. Addressing these issues requires interdisciplinary collaboration and sustainable practices.

Health and Ecological Implications

Siddiqui et al. (2022) highlighted the environmental and health risks associated with waste landfilling, stressing the need to assess its broader impacts—particularly the dangers of illegal and uncontrolled dumpsites in developing countries. Palomeras et al. (2020) called for consistent, efficient sanitary landfill management and strict compliance with RA 9003 to prevent adverse public health and environmental outcomes in nearby communities. Saha et al. (2023) reported elevated heavy metal levels in the Mid-Brahmaputra Valley, India, due to landfill leachate, emphasizing the need for regular monitoring and government action. Similarly, Hussein et al. (2020) found that non-sanitary landfills in Malaysia posed greater environmental and health hazards compared to sanitary ones. Collectively, these studies

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highlight the urgent need to address soil and groundwater contamination through strict monitoring and effective waste management to safeguard public health and biodiversity.

Heavy metal contamination from leachate poses risks to water quality, human health, and ecosystems, particularly for communities near landfills, requiring rigorous monitoring and government action to ensure sustainable waste management. Addressing environmental contamination and pollution necessitates interdisciplinary collaboration, technological innovation, and sustainable practices to safeguard ecosystems and human health against global challenges.

Despite the significant steps taken to address solid waste management in the Philippines, particularly through the establishment of the Bayombong Sanitary Landfill, critical gaps in the understanding of its environmental and social impacts remain. Although the landfill underwent thorough regulatory processes, including an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) and the issuance of an Environmental Compliance Certificate (ECC), there has been no subsequent, comprehensive study evaluating its long-term effects on groundwater and soil quality in the surrounding communities. The lack of empirical data on the environmental contamination caused by leachate percolation—especially its impact on the local ecosystem and public health—presents a significant gap in both policy and scientific knowledge. Additionally, while national laws like RA 9003 and studies from other regions emphasize the importance of proper landfill management, there is insufficient localized research to guide effective mitigation strategies for the Bayombong SLF's environmental challenges. This study aimed to fill these gaps by providing data-driven insights into the contamination risks associated with the landfill, thus enabling better-informed decisions for local waste management practices and community health protection.

Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to assess the environmental impact of pollutants, particularly heavy metals and organic compounds, at the Sanitary Landfill Facility site in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. The primary objectives were to characterize the physicochemical properties of soil, groundwater, and leachate samples from various landfill cells, focusing on their composition and contamination levels. Specifically, the study sought to analyze the concentrations of lead and cadmium in the soil samples and evaluate the potential risks to both human health and the ecosystem. Additionally, the study aimed to develop a Sustainable Remediation Plan tailored to minimize the environmental impact of the landfill and ensure its long-term sustainability.

METHODOLOGY

Design

The study utilized a quasi-experimental research design to assess the physicochemical characteristics of soil, groundwater, and leachate samples collected from within the landfill site in terms of heavy metals and organic compounds in Bayombong Sanitary Landfill.

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Study Site and Sample Collection

The Sanitary Landfill Facility (SLF) and Materials Recovery Facility (MRF) in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya are situated at Purok 7 of Barangays Magsaysay and Busilac, with coordinates approximately 16°29'14.51"N, 121°06'30.69"E (Lat/Long, WGS 1984 datum). This location spans 8.0296 hectares within the Timberland/Forest Zone owned and managed by the Local Government Unit of Bayombong. The ownership is supported by an Approved Survey Plan Swo- (aff-02-000052 dated September 28, 2007). The Environmental Compliance Certificate (ECC) issued by the EMB R02, with ECC Reference No. ECC-R02-0812-250-9999 on December 12, 2008, validates its compliance with environmental regulations.

The groundwater, leachate, and soil samples were collected at the landfill site at Barangay Upper Magsaysay, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, as shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1.
 Vicinity Map of the
 Bayombong Sanitary
 Landfill Facility

The facility comprises seven cells, with Cell 4 currently in use, covering an area of 2,592 m² and an estimated 12,960 cu.m capacity. The SLF/MRF complex includes various components such as Garbage Cells, a Gate, a Water Tank, a Fruit Tree Plantation, a Guard House, an Interior Road, Buffer Zone, Windrows/Heap Type Composting Facility, Leachate Pond, Bambusetum, Administration Building with Septic Tank, Multi-purpose and Livelihood Building, Equipment Pool, Perimeter Fence, Filter Pond, Monitoring Wells, Leachate Conveyor Pipe, Roadway Drainage, Special Waste Vault, and Toxic and Hazardous Waste Facility.

These components collectively facilitate efficient waste management, ensuring proper segregation, collection, recycling, and disposal of solid waste while adhering to environmental standards and regulations. Additionally, the strategic location, approximately 7 kilometers from the central business district, minimizes the impact on populated areas while serving the municipality's waste management needs.

The physicochemical characterization (Test for nitrite and phosphate) was conducted at the Center for Natural Sciences Research Laboratory of Saint Mary's University. Heavy metals were tested at the National Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, University of the Philippines-Los Baños using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS).

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1. Sample Collection and Preparation

Soil samples were collected from four quadrants within each of the four accessible landfill cells to ensure representative coverage. On-site assessments documented physical properties such as soil type and general environmental conditions. Chemical samples were taken from a depth of 15–20 cm using a clean trowel, stored in sterile polyethylene bags, and oven-dried at 40°C for 24 hours in the laboratory. The samples were then cleaned and homogenized for analysis.

Groundwater and leachate samples were collected in plastic bottles, which were first rinsed with a representative sample to avoid contamination. The bottles were filled to the brim to prevent air space and oxidation, then tightly sealed to maintain sample integrity. These samples were transported to the research laboratory for comprehensive chemical characterization, including tests for nitrates and phosphates.

2. Data Gathering Procedure:

2.1 Determination of pH

The pH of the soil was measured using a Takemura Soil pH Tester by directly inserting the probe into multiple locations within each landfill cell. Readings were recorded once the needle stabilized to ensure accuracy. For leachate samples, pH was determined by collecting samples from the designated leachate collection area within the landfill. These were then analyzed using an ATAGO digital pH meter.

2.2 Determination of Nitrogen

2.2.1 Nitrogen in the Soil

A Kjeldahl distillation was conducted to determine the nitrogen content of the soil. Twenty grams of soil were weighed and transferred to a Kjeldahl flask, moistened with 10 mL of distilled water, and rinsed down the neck. To this, 100 mL of 0.32% KMnO_4 , 100 mL of 2.5% NaOH , and glass beads were added to prevent bumping. The flask was stoppered, and a distillation apparatus was set up. A receiving flask containing 25 mL of 0.01 M H_2SO_4 with 3–4 drops of methyl red was prepared, and the delivery tube was immersed in it. The mixture was heated to distill approximately 100 mL of ammonia over 30 minutes. The remaining acid in the receiving flask was then titrated with 0.02 M NaOH to determine the amount of ammonia distilled.

2.2.2 Nitrogen in Leachates

Nitrogen determination in leachates was performed using two methods. The first method utilized the chromotropic acid technique to measure available nitrite, with modifications to the standard procedure. A standard curve was prepared by diluting a 1 mg/mL sodium nitrate stock solution in 0.1 mg/mL increments (0 to 1.0 mg/mL). Both the standard and 10 mL of each leachate sample were acidified with sulfuric acid, followed by the addition of chromotropic acid. After a 6-minute development period, absorbance at 410 nm was measured for both the standard and leachate samples, and the results were recorded.

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The second method employed a HANNA reagent set to measure available ammonia. Two drops of EDTA solution were added to 10 mL of each leachate sample, followed by eight drops of Nessler's solution. The mixture was shaken until an orange color developed, and the intensity of the color was compared to a provided cuvette to estimate ammonia concentration, with a maximum detection limit of 2.5 mg/mL.

2.3 Determination of Phosphates in the Soil

The available phosphorus in soil was determined using Bray's P-1 extraction method. A 2g soil sample was combined with 20 mL of Bray's P-1 reagent in a 50 mL vessel and shaken for 5 minutes. A blank was prepared with only the reagent. The mixture was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper, and the filtrate was collected. For color development, 5 mL of the filtered extract was mixed with ammonium molybdate and stannous chloride solutions, then diluted and the absorbance measured at 660 nm using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer. A calibration curve was prepared using standard solutions with known phosphorus concentrations, and the absorbance data was used to determine the phosphorus concentration in the soil samples.

2.4 Determination of Heavy Metals

Before heavy metals analysis, the samples were digested in aqua regia (a 3:1 ratio of 35% HCl and 70% high-purity HNO₃) and filtered. Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) was then used to determine the concentrations of heavy metals, as outlined by Uddin et al. (2016) for its efficiency. AAS operates on the principle that excited atoms absorb energy at specific wavelengths, resulting in a decrease in signal energy proportional to concentration. Each element has unique sensitivity characteristics, with the calibration curve range defined by noise and linearity. The optical system was configured with a hollow cathode lamp for the target element, and the appropriate slit and wavelength were selected. A standard solution of known analyte concentration was aspirated, and the sample concentration was determined by interpolating from the absorbance reading. The concentrations of Cd and Hg in the samples were successfully analyzed using AAS.

Treatment of Data

Measures of central tendency were employed to analyze the collected data, specifically the arithmetic mean. The mean value was used to summarize and represent the general trend of the values obtained from the various sampling sites and conditions. This statistical approach allowed for a simplified comparison between different data sets, providing insight into the overall behavior or characteristics of the measured parameters.

Ethical Considerations

This study, approved by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB 2024 0678), involved measuring nitrate and phosphate levels in groundwater and soil from a landfill site, without involving human or animal participants. Strict safety protocols were followed due to the hazardous chemicals used, ensuring all procedures generating potential aerosols were conducted in controlled laboratory environments. The intellectual property

of the research output belongs to Saint Mary's University, with the researchers recognized as the authors. In accordance with the SMU Project WEALTH 2.0 guidelines and university policies, the final results will be shared during the Linggo ng Likha at Lingkod event and through national and international publications and conferences, reflecting the commitment to contributing valuable insights to the academic community and advancing environmental risk assessment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Section 1. Characterization of Physico-Chemical Properties of Soil Samples from Landfill Site

This section presents the physical and chemical characteristics of soil samples collected from various cells of the landfill site.

Table 1 summarizes the physical properties of soil samples collected from four cells of the landfill site. The parameters assessed include soil temperature (°C), soil color, and soil type.

Table 1. Physical Properties of Soil Samples from Various Cells of the Landfill Site

Parameters	Average per Cell			
	Cell 1	Cell 2	Cell 3	Cell 4
Soil Temperature (°C)	30.5	28.3	28.5	28.5
Soil Color	Dark brown	Dark brown	Dark brown	Dark brown
Soil Type	Clay-loam	Clay-loam	Clay-loam	Clay-loam

The soil across all four sampling cells in Barangay Upper Magsaysay, Bayombong, and Nueva Vizcaya displayed a consistent clay-loam structure and dark brown coloration. This suggests a uniformity in soil texture and organic matter throughout the site; clay-loam soils are recognized for their balanced sand, silt, and clay composition, which offers good water retention and aeration.

Ambient temperature readings ranged from 28.5 °C to 30.5°C, with Cell 1 recording the highest temperature (30.5°C), while Cells 3 and 4 shared the lowest temperature at 28.5°C. Although Cells 1 and 2 had the most plant cover, ambient temperature was recorded close to midday; hence, temperature readings were slightly higher. Cell 1 had a lot of plant biodiversity because it had been closed for the longest time, while cell two was recently closed but had been planted with bamboo and fruit-bearing Guyabano trees.

Table 2 presents the average chemical properties of soil samples collected from four different cells within the landfill site. The parameters measured include soil pH, nitrogen (kg/ha), and phosphorus (kg/ha) levels.

Table 2. Chemical Properties of Soil Samples from Various Cells of the Landfill Site

Parameters	Average per Cell			
	Cell 1	Cell 2	Cell 3	Cell 4
pH	5.6	5.2	5.7	6.0
Nitrogen (kg/ha)	106.65	75.264	75.264	56.448
Phosphorus (kg/ha)	3.270	4.550	1.170	3.085

Each cell's soil pH level exhibited a slightly acidic pH range (5.2-6.0). Cell 4 has an acceptable pH level since it falls within the optimum pH described by Dewangan et al. (2023) for most plants, while Cells 1, 2, and 3 had slightly lower pH levels. This indicates that most of the sites may experience nutrient availability limitations due to suboptimal pH levels; acidic conditions are known to limit phosphorus availability and can alter microbial communities critical for nutrient cycling.

The average soil nitrogen concentrations for each cell were tested, which showed that among the cells, cell 1 had the highest amount of nitrogen content, 106.65 kg/ha, while cells 2, 3, and 4 had 75.264, 75.264, and 56.448 kg/ha, respectively. While there is no standardized acceptable range for nitrogen concentration in soil (Kitpakornsanti et al., 2022), the significant variation suggests uneven nutrient distribution, possibly linked to the differences in human intervention, microbial activity, or organic content. Site-specific supplementation may be necessary to ensure optimum growth of plant cover across the landfill sites.

Furthermore, this result also supports the study of Adame et al. (2018), which found that total nitrogen increased with forest age. Cell 1 had been closed for the longest time; hence, plant vegetation was able to develop significantly. This result confirms that nitrogen accumulation on the surface layer reflects the soil and biomass deposition with time, as nutrient content is primarily stored in the surface soil (Ngaba et al., 2020). In other parameters, phosphorus content for cells 1 and 4 is within the acceptable range. In contrast, cell 2 slightly exceeded the acceptable range, while cell 3 is below the acceptable range, according to Xe et al. (2023). This deficiency may restrict root development and energy in plant covers if not addressed. Cells 1, 2, and 4 displayed phosphorus levels within/near the acceptable range, indicating sufficient availability except cell 3. Localized phosphorus enrichment is suggested for this site.

Section 2. Characterization of Chemical Properties of Groundwater and Leachate Samples from Landfill site

The characterization of chemical properties of water samples obtained from Bayombong Ecological Park and Sanitary Landfill, Magsaysay, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Chemical Properties of Groundwater and Leachate Samples from Landfill site

Site of Collection	Ammonia	Nitrite
Leachate Treatment Well 1 (L1): <i>Obligate-anaerobic Bacteria</i>	>2.5 mg/L	0.8 mg/L
Leachate Treatment Well 2 (L2): <i>Facultative-anaerobic Bacteria</i>	2.5 mg/L	0.6 mg/L
Leachate Treatment Well 3 (L3): <i>Obligate-aerobic Bacteria</i>	2.0 mg/L	0.2 mg/L
Tap Water (H): <i>Groundwater Representative</i>	1.0 mg/L	<0.2 mg/L

Water samples were collected from sequential effluent treatment wells (L1, L2, L3) at a landfill site and from an on-site tap water source (H). The treatment process progresses from anaerobic (L1) to facultative-anaerobic (L2) and aerobic (L3) stages, followed by filtration prior to discharge.

Ammonia concentrations decreased progressively across treatment stages: 4.2 mg/L in L1, 2.5 mg/L in L2, and 2.0 mg/L in L3. The tap water sample (H) contained ammonia at <1.0 mg/L. Nitrite was detected in all treatment wells but not quantified due to its instability, while nitrate persisted in post-treatment effluent. Compliance testing against DENR standards (DAO No. 19, s. 2021) confirmed that L3 met the General Effluent Standard (GES) ammonia limit (2.0 mg/L) but exceeded the Water Quality Guideline (WQG) for safe discharge into natural water bodies. Post-filtration effluent sampling was precluded by system inaccessibility. The observed ammonia reduction (L1 to L3) aligns with microbial degradation dynamics documented in landfill leachate treatment systems (DAO No. 19, s. 2021). Elevated ammonia in L1 (4.2 mg/L) likely originates from anaerobic hydrolysis of organic nitrogen compounds, a process consistent with findings by Smith et al. (2020). The modest reduction in L2 (2.5 mg/L) under facultative-anaerobic conditions suggests limited nitrification activity, whereas the aerobic environment in L3 promotes ammonia oxidation via nitrifying bacteria.

Section 3. Analysis of Heavy Metals in Soil Samples from Landfill Site

Section 3 presents the results of heavy metal analysis in soil samples collected from the four accessible landfill cells. Table 4 summarizes the average concentrations of cadmium (in µg/kg) and lead (in mg/kg) detected per cell.

Table 4. Heavy Metals in Soil Samples from Landfill Site

Parameters	Average per Cell			
	Cell 1	Cell 2	Cell 3	Cell 4
Cadmium (µg/kg)	11.26	15.26	14.91	15.66
Lead (mg/kg)	0.42	0.73	0.82	0.99

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As shown in Table 4, soil samples from all landfill cells exhibited low concentrations of cadmium and lead, suggesting minimal deposition of industrial or manufacturing waste. The analysis revealed lead and cadmium levels below 5 mg/kg, well beneath the hazardous waste thresholds set by the EPA, as noted in ACTenviro (2024). These low heavy metal concentrations indicate a reduced risk of environmental contamination. Both lead and cadmium are persistent toxins that can leach into groundwater or accumulate in ecosystems; however, the observed levels imply that the landfill primarily contains residual wastes and that household hazardous wastes, such as batteries and electronics, have been effectively contained.

Additionally, the landfill cells are equipped with HDPE liners, and the clay-loam soil texture likely aids in metal immobilization. Clay particles bind to cationic metals, limiting their migration into the surrounding environment (Luo et al., 2025).

This finding has important implications for human and ecological health. The reduced leaching of heavy metals decreases the risk of groundwater contamination, which is a major exposure pathway for lead and cadmium in humans. For ecosystems, the threat of bioaccumulation is minimized within the landfill, reducing the likelihood of terrestrial species ingesting toxic amounts through soil, water, or food chains.

Section 4. Bioremediation Plan

Essential soil nutrients, including nitrogen and phosphorus, were present at trace levels, reflecting a nutrient-poor environment. Field observations identified uneven nutrient distribution, likely exacerbated by human-induced erosion. Despite these conditions, vegetation such as bamboo and fruiting trees like Guyabano thrived in closed landfill cells. The landfill manager confirmed the recent implementation of initial phytoremediation strategies targeting these species. The low heavy metal concentrations suggest limited industrial waste influx, reducing immediate contamination risks. However, the nutrient-deficient soil underscores the challenges of ecological restoration in landfills, particularly when compounded by erosion-driven heterogeneity. Colonizing bamboo and hardy fruiting species in closed cells highlight their adaptability to degraded environments, aligning with the landfill's nascent phytoremediation efforts.

Bamboo's success in nutrient-poor soils reinforces its documented role in stabilizing degraded landscapes and sequestering trace pollutants (Emamverdian et al., 2017). Similarly, the resilience of Guyabano and Guava—species known for tolerating marginal soils—supports their inclusion in bioremediation frameworks. However, the utility of fruiting species requires caution: while they may aid soil stabilization, their produce risks bioaccumulation of contaminants, even at low heavy metal levels. Comprehensive testing of heavy metals, organic pollutants, and nutrient content is essential before considering these fruits safe for human consumption. The findings from the previous sections of the study validate the landfill's focus on bamboo as a priority species for micro-environmental restoration, given its dual capacity for soil stabilization and low contaminant uptake. Future efforts should expand monitoring to assess long-term phytoremediation efficacy and quantify risks associated with fruiting species to balance ecological and public health goals.

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Compliance with regulatory standards for heavy metals confirms the landfill's commitment to safe waste management. However, ongoing monitoring is critical, as even trace concentrations may accumulate over time—especially if waste inputs trend toward industrial sources. Proactive strategies, such as improving waste segregation or introducing phytoremediation to absorb metals, could mitigate potential long-term risks.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The environmental assessment of the Barangay Upper Magsaysay landfill shows a landscape shaped by human activity and natural conditions. The clay-loam texture and dark brown color suggest moderate organic matter, balanced water retention, and aeration. However, slightly acidic pH (5.2–6.0) may limit phosphorus availability, affecting plant growth. Cell 1, closed the longest, has the highest nitrogen level (106.65 kg/ha), while Cell 3 shows phosphorus deficiency, requiring enrichment. Heavy metal levels, particularly cadmium and lead, are below hazardous thresholds, indicating minimal industrial input and effective containment. The soil composition reduces metal leaching risks, protecting groundwater.

Leachate treatment shows effective ammonia reduction, though the final effluent exceeds discharge standards, indicating the need for further treatment. Vegetation, including bamboo and guyabano trees, shows potential for phytoremediation, with bamboo being a strategic choice for soil stabilization. However, fruiting species pose bioaccumulation risks and require testing before consumption.

Recommendations include addressing pH imbalances, supplementing nutrients, optimizing wastewater treatment, and prioritizing non-food phytoremediation species. Long-term monitoring of heavy metals, nutrients, and vegetation health is essential for balancing ecological recovery with public safety. With sustained interventions, this landfill could serve as a model for rehabilitating degraded environments while prioritizing community health.

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